

Potentiometric Studies on Complexation Equilibria between some Transition Metal Ions and 2-(Phenylhydrazono)butanoic Acid in Ethanol-Water Medium

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The binary (1 : 1, 1 : 2) and ternary (1 : 1 : 1) metal complex formation constants of 2-(phenylhydrazono)butanoic acid (PHB) with bivalent Mn, Co, Ni, Cu and Zn ions have been determined potentiometrically at 20, 30, 40 and 50° in 40, 50, 60 and 70 (v/v) ethanol-water mixtures at 0.10 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. The other chelating agents functioning as secondary ligands include catechol, ethylenediamine, proline, hydroxyproline, β -alanine and glycine while those acting as primary ones consist of 1,10-phenanthroline and salicylic acid. Thermodynamic parameters, differences in stability constants and percentages of distribution of various chelated species have been evaluated and discussed in terms of the basicity of ligands, statistical aspects, electrostatic interaction, metal-ligand π -interaction, denticity, nature of donor sites and stereochemical aspects.

Various phenylhydrazones of α -keto propanoic and butanoic acids and their metal complexes serve as antibacterial, antifungal, herbicidal, insecticidal and therapeutic agents¹. 2-(Phenylhydrazono)butanoic acid (PHB) is also used in metabolic studies in animals². With a view to understanding the nature of metal-ligand interactions and bonding in the complexes of PHB, binary stability constants with Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II} and Zn^{II}, and ternary formation constants with Cu^{II} involving other chelating agents such as catechol (Cat), ethylenediamine (en), proline (Pro), hydroxyproline (Hpro), β -alanine (Ala), glycine (Gly), 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen) and salicylic acid (SA) have been determined at 20, 30, 40 and 50° in 40, 50, 60 and 70% (v/v) ethanol-water mixtures at 0.10 M (KNO₃) ionic strength. Thermodynamic parameters (ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS°) are evaluated and separated into their corresponding electrostatic (ΔG_c° and ΔH_c°) and non-electrostatic or cratic (ΔG_e° and ΔH_e°) components to understand the extent of ionic and covalent nature persisting in these complexes.

Results and Discussion

The evidence for the formation of chelates of PHB with bivalent transition metal ions have been obtained from the pH titration data. The \bar{n} values obtained before the formation of the precipitates for the metal ions were found in the range between 0.1–2.0 indicating the formation of both 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal-ligand chelates. The order of stabilities was found to be: Mn^{II} < Co^{II} < Ni^{II} < Cu^{II} > Zn^{II}. This sequence is in accordance with the Irving-Williams series³. This order is particularly important because it is valid for most oxygen and nitrogen donor ligands irrespective of the structure of the ligand. The values of ΔG° , ΔH° and ΔS° for 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 metal complexes have been calculated by using Gibbs-Helmholtz equation. To know the extent of ionic and covalent nature of bonding in these complexes, the ΔG° and ΔH° were separated into their electrostatic (ΔG_c° and ΔH_c°) and cratic (ΔG_e° and ΔH_e°) components as suggested by Degischer and Nancollas⁴. Comparison of these

values for the equilibrium (1),

indicates that ΔG_c° and ΔH_c° values are significantly more negative than ΔG_e° and ΔH_e° values, suggesting non-electrostatic forces being stronger than the electrostatic forces in 1 : 1 chelates. The difference in the electrostatic and cratic components decreases in the order: Cu^{II} < Ni^{II} > Co^{II} > Mn^{II}, which shows that ionic character increases in the order: Cu^{II} < Ni^{II} < Co^{II} < Mn^{II}. Since the number of unpaired electrons also increases in the same order, it may be concluded that ionic character of the complexes increases with the increase in the number of unpaired electrons.

Basolo and Murmann⁵ reported the effect of solvent on complexes containing N-metal links and concluded that the organic content of the solvent had little influence on the stabilities of complexes. Van Uitert *et al.*⁶ observed that the stability of complexes which contained O-metal links, increased by an increase in the organic content of the solvent. The present complexes contained both O-metal and N-metal links, and hence the observed increase in the stabilities may be due to the O-metal link which is strongly affected⁷. The values are given in Table 1.

In the ternary systems of the Cu^{II} metal complexes, the mixed ligand M-A-L curves closely follow those of the 1 : 1 M-A binary curves in the lower pH region (pH < 3.5) until the protons of this primary ligand under study (A) are neutralised, indicating the formation of binary M-A complexes and non-coordination of L with M^{II} ions in this region. The divergence of the ternary M-A-L curves from the binary M-A systems above this region reveals the formation of ternary complexes of the type M-A-L in two-step equilibria (eqs. 2 and 3):

where, A = PHB, L = other secondary chelating agents, i.e. Cat, en, Pro, Hpro, Ala or Gly and L' = other primary chelat-

TABLE 1—PROTON-LIGAND AND METAL-LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF 2-(PHENYLHYDRAZONO)BUTANOIC ACID IN DIFFERENT PERCENTAGES OF ETHANOL-WATER MIXTURES

 Temp. = 303 K, $\mu = 0.10 M (KNO_3)$

%Org. Sol.		D	1/D	N ₂	H ⁺	Mn ^{II}	Co ^{II}	Ni ^{II}	Cu ^{II}	Zn ^{II}
By vol.	By wt.									
40	32	53	0.018	0.174 8	5.70	2.95 (2.35)	3.12 (2.55)	3.50 (2.67)	4.81 (4.01)	3.01 (2.52)
50	40	47	0.021	0.241 0	5.90	3.12 (2.46)	3.33 (2.67)	3.66 (2.79)	5.05 (4.18)	3.21 (2.63)
60	48	42	0.024	0.322 7	6.13	3.42 (2.66)	3.58 (2.80)	3.91 (2.79)	5.30 (4.36)	3.43 (2.83)
70	56	37	0.027	0.425 7	6.40	3.62 (2.77)	3.76 (2.92)	4.01 (2.95)	5.54 (4.53)	3.64 (2.93)

 Figures in the parentheses indicate the values of $\log K_2$.

ing ligands, i.e. Phen or SA. The formation of ternary complexes is further supported by the non-super imposable nature of the theoretical composite curves in the region of mixed ligand complex formation⁸. The $\Delta \log K$ (or $\Delta \log K'$) values⁹ alongwith their ternary complex formation constants, $\log K_T$ or $\log K'_T$ for all the systems are given in Table 2. The $\Delta \log K$ (or $\Delta \log K'$) values of the Cu^{II} ternary complexes are -0.9 to -1.1 , indicating that these complexes have a distorted octahedral geometry. Hence, an experimentally determined value of $\Delta \log K$ (or $\Delta \log K'$) > -0.9 indicates the extrastabilisation in ternary complexes formed.

From the knowledge of proton-ligand and metal-ligand formation constants, the distribution of the total metal among various metal-ligand species as a function of pH is calculated by a computer programme BEST due to Martell and Motekaitis¹⁰. As a representative case, the distribution diagrams of Cu^{II} with PHB involving the O,O, N,N and N,O chelating agents such as SA, en and Pro are given in

Figs. 1–3. These diagrams also reveal that the formation of ternary complexes occurs in a stepwise manner.

Excepting the case of Cu-A-Cat system, the $\Delta \log K$ values for all the other ternary system were found to be negative, indicating that the secondary ligand (L) binds

 Fig. 1. Distribution diagram for Cu^{II}-SA-PHB system.

 Fig. 2. Distribution diagram for Cu^{II}-PHB-en system.

 TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF BINARY AND TERNARY METAL CHELATES OF Cu^{II} AND 2-(PHENYLHYDRAZONO)BUTANOIC ACID INVOLVING OTHER CHELATING AGENTS*

 Temp. = 303 K, medium : 40% (v/v) ethanol-water, $\mu = 0.10 M (KNO_3)$

Other chelating agents	Ternary system	Ternary St. Cont. $\log K_T$	Binary St. Cont. $\log K'_T$	Difference in St. Cont. $(-)\Delta \log K$
Catechol	PHB-Cat	12.18	12.15	+0.03
Ethylenediamine	PHB-en	9.95	10.72	0.77
Proline	PHB-Pro	7.93	8.90	0.97
Hydroxyproline	PHB-Hpro	7.45	8.49	1.04
β -Alanine	PHB-Ala	7.47	8.20	0.73
Glycine	PHB-Gly	7.27	8.30	1.03

	$\log K'_T$	$\log K^A_T$	$(-)\Delta \log K'$	
1,10-Phenanthroline	Phen-PHB	5.87	4.81	+1.06
Salicylic acid	SA-PHB	3.71	4.81	1.10

*The difference in stability constants is calculated by the relationship : $\Delta \log K = \log K_T - \log K'_T$ or $\Delta \log K' = \log K^A_T - \log K'_T$.

better to Cu^{II} ion than to the binary Cu-A primary complex. Such a lowering of stabilities of ternary complexes compared to that of binary chelates may be due to the greater destabilisation effect¹¹ caused by the ligand repulsion in the mixed ligand complexes than that in the binary system,

Fig. 3. Distribution diagram for Cu^{II} -PHB-Pro system

coupled with the availability of lesser number of coordinating sites for the secondary ligand on the primary complex Cu-A compared to free Cu^{II} (aq) ion¹². In the case of Cu-A-Cat system, the $\Delta \log K$ values are observed to be less negative confirming that Cat binds better to the binary Cu-A primary complex than to Cu^{II} (aq) ion. A comparison of these statistical considerations reveals that the order of stability of ternary complexes with respect to 'the other chelating ligands L' in terms of donor atoms is found to be $\text{O,O} > \text{N,N} > \text{N,O}$, i.e. $\text{Cat} > \text{en} > \text{Pro} > \text{Hpro} > \text{Ala} > \text{Gly}$. This sequence is in accordance with their basicity order and denticity nature, because for a series of similar ligands the higher the basicity of the ligand, the greater is the stability of the complex. Thus, one of the main conclusions is that ligand PHB, when it is acting as primary ligand, has an increasing stabilisation effect (positive or less negative $\Delta \log K$) on the formation of a ternary complex with ligand containing oxygen as donor atoms, and when ligand PHB acts as a secondary ligand, and some of 'the other chelating ligands L', where $L' = \text{phen}$ and SA , act as primary ligands, the order of stabilities of ternary complexes becomes as, $\text{N,N} > \text{O,O}$ i.e. $\text{Phen} > \text{SA}$. The $\Delta \log K'$ values in Cu-Phen-A system is less negative indicating that the neutral Phen molecule stabilises the formation of the primary complex Cu-Phen by way of conjugation in the ligand system and metal-ligand dn-pn interactions leading to a high resultant positive charge on the central metal ion forcing it to coordinate strongly with secondary ligand¹³. Electrostatic attraction between primary complex, Cu-Phen and the secondary ligand A also facilitates the formation of ternary complex. In the case of SA, it was observed by Verma *et al.*¹⁴ that it would act as a primary ligand in the presence of N,O donors such as hippuric acid. In the present study also, SA is functioning as a primary ligand in presence of N,O donor, i.e. PHB. SA on primary coordination with the metal ion would partially neutralise the positive charge on it and diminish electrostatic attraction between the primary complex Cu-SA and the secondary ligand A. This would lead to lower stabilities of the formation of

ternary complexes and hence the observed order is justified.

The dependence of ternary formation constants on temperature has been carried out with Cu^{II} ion systems. Though both the enthalpy and entropy factors are favourable for the formation of ternary complexes, entropy factor appears to be the driving force, i.e. $\log K_T > \log K_2$, when compared to the corresponding binary systems of secondary ligands. The $\log K_T$ values for these metal chelates were found to be slightly less than those of $\log K_1$ values indicating that the destabilisation of ternary chelates caused by enthalpy changes is more prominent than the stabilisation induced by the entropy changes. Again, the values of ΔG_C° and ΔH_C° are significantly more negative than ΔG_e° and ΔH_e° , suggesting more covalent character of bonds in Cu^{II} ternary chelates.

Experimental

Ligand PHB was prepared by dissolving phenylhydrazine hydrochloride and α -ketobutyric acid in a little ethanol². All the other chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The pH titrations were carried out in 40% (v/v) ethanol-water medium and the appropriate corrections were made¹⁵. In addition, titrations were also carried out in 50, 60 and 70% (v/v) ethanol-water mixtures to study the effect of variation in dielectric constant of the medium on complexation reactions. An inert atmosphere was maintained throughout the titrations by bubbling continuously oxygen-free pre-saturated nitrogen gas to keep away either oxygen or carbon dioxide. The values of \bar{n}_A , $\text{p}K_1$, $\text{p}K_2$, \bar{n} , $\text{p}L$, $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ were calculated by Irving and Rossotti titration technique¹⁶. The formation constants of ternary metal chelates were evaluated by the method of Santappa and Ramamoorthy¹⁷.

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